

Check what SPATIAL has accomplished in one year

Over the past year, the SPATIAL team achieved great results and set the pace for the work to be performed in the following year.

[Learn more](#)

Prachi Bagabe, researcher at TU Delft, explains her PHD work and her involvement in SPATIAL.

[Read the editorial](#)

First SPATIAL Consortium meeting, held in September 2022, was hosted by Fraunhofer Fokus in Berlin.

[Learn more](#)

Our collaborators:

The ARCADIAN-IoT project, under the same call as SPATIAL, shared an article for the SPATIAL website about IoT and Data

Protection.
It is available at this [link](#).

SPATIAL - info@spatial-h2020.eu

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